

The Dissociation Constants of Salicylic and Sulphosalicylic Acids in Mixed Solvents

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The dissociation constants of the ligands salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acid in different percentages of dioxane-water mixtures have been measured spectrophotometrically. The thermodynamic properties of the ligands have also been determined at the two high percentages (70% and 82% by weight of dioxane) of organic solvent to have some knowledge about the role of the solvent on the dissociation constants of the ligands.

The ligands, salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acid, have been widely studied due to their complex forming ability with various metals particularly as analytical reagents in the colorimetric estimation of Ferric ion. The dissociation constants of the ligands were determined in aqueous solutions by a number of workers¹.

In order to find out the role of the solvent on the dissociation constants of the ligands and their complexes, we have studied the dissociation constants of the carboxyl groups of the ligands in 20%, 30%, 45%, 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane-water mixtures at $\mu = 0.1M$ and $\mu = 0$ at 25° spectrophotometrically. The effect of solvent on the other thermodynamic parameters ΔH and ΔS , have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acids of reagent quality (E. Merck) were estimated volumetrically. Dioxane (A.R.-B.D.H.) was refluxed for 48 hr. with NaOH, distilled twice and then it was treated with metallic sodium, kept overnight and finally distilled. The dioxane thus obtained was kept in an atmosphere of nitrogen and was utilised within 48 hr.

Stock solutions of the ligands were prepared by dissolving the ligands in dioxane. Caustic soda, formic acid, perchloric acid and other chemicals were of E. Merck's reagent quality.

For the determination of dissociation constant of salicylic acid at $\mu = 0.1M$, sodium formate formic acid buffers were used whereas $HClO_4$ acid was used to adjust the acidity in the determination of the dissociation constants of salicylic acid at $\mu = 0$ and sulphosalicylic acid at $\mu = 0.1M$ and $\mu = 0$.

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1. Stability constants, Part I, Ed. J. Bjerrum, G. Schwarzenbach and L. G. Sillen. The Chemical Society, London, 1957, pp. 53 and 56.

The ligands absorb strongly in the U.V. region. It has been found that the wavelength of maximum absorption in strongly acid medium shifts slightly towards the longer wavelength regions with the increase in the percentage of organic solvent.

To determine the dissociation constant of the ligands, optical densities of the ligands in a number of formic acid-formate buffer solutions as well as in solutions of perchloric acid having intermediate pH 's were measured. Optical densities (o.d.'s) of molecular forms and ionic forms, in solutions, $N/10$ and $N/5$ $HClO_4$ and slightly alkaline medium (pH about 10) were also measured. The blank solutions were of the same composition as in the experimental solutions except the ligands. O.d.'s of the solutions were measured at 25° in case of dioxane-water solvents containing 20%, 30% and 45% by weight of dioxane and for mixed solvents having 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane at 25° , 35° and 45° at $310 m\mu$ and $315 m\mu$'s with Beckman DU spectrophotometer fitted with thermostatic device.

Measurements of Hydrogen ion concentrations in mixed-solvents.

Calibration of glass electrode : As we pass from aqueous solution to mixed solvents the glass electrode potentials change and the liquid junction potential of uncertain magnitudes may vitiate the results. In order to overcome this, it is necessary to calibrate the glass electrode in different solvent mixtures. Following Van Uitert *et al.*², the meter readings in mixed solvents are referred to as B values. To calibrate the glass electrode, $10^{-4}M$ $HClO_4$ acid solutions in mixed solvents (20%, 30%, 45%, 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane) were measured against $10^{-4}M$ $HClO_4$ acid in aqueous solution as well as against $M/20$ Potassium biphthalate buffer. The correction factor was calculated from the relationship

$$-\log[H^+] = B + \log U_H$$

where $[H^+]$ is the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration assuming 100% dissociation of the acid in aqueous and mixed solvents. The B-values of the solutions, measured with Cambridge bench type battery operated pH -meter, were corrected to get $-\log[H^+]$ of different solutions. A comparison of pH -values obtained from the formic acid and formate buffer based on Harned's³ value for the dissociation constant of formic acid in mixed solvents with the actually measured values followed by correction for ionic strength in the changed dielectric constant reveal that the values of H^+ -ion concentration obtained from both the types of measurements are in good agreement upto 70% by weight of dioxane. In mixed-solvent with 82% by weight of dioxane the deviation is quite appreciable, which, however, appears to be quite reasonable at this high percentage of dioxane.

Activity coefficients at different temperatures and at different percentages of mixed solvents were calculated with the help of Debye-Hückel equation with appropriate values of A and B due to the change in dielectric constant. Dielectric constants were taken from Akerlof's data⁴. Ion-size parameter α° for the ligands has been taken as 6\AA ⁵. The calculated values and the experimental values for HCl as measured by Harned and co-workers agree fairly well upto 70% by weight of dioxane.

2. L. G. Van Uitert and C. G. Haas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
3. H. S. Harned and B. B. Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolyte solutions" ,3rd ed., Reinhold Publishing Corp, New York, N.Y., 1958, pp. 667 and 756.
4. G. Akerlof, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4125; G. Akerlof and O. A. Short, *ibid.*, 1936, **58**, 1241.
5. Treatise on Analytical Chemistry, Part I, Vol. I, Edited by I. M. Kolthoff and P. J. Elving, The Interscience Encyclopedia, Inc. New York, p. 243, 1959.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dissociation reaction for salicylic acid can be represented as

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant is given by

$$pK_T = B + \log U_H - \log \frac{d_M - d}{d - d_i} - 2 \log f_{\pm}$$

whereas,

$$pK_C = B + \log U_H - \log \frac{d_M - d}{d - d_i}.$$

For sulphosalicylic acid $\text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{A}^-$,

$$pK_T = B + \log U_H - \log \frac{d_M - d}{d - d_i} - 4 \log f_{\pm}$$

(since $f_{\text{H}^+} = f_{\text{HA}^-}$ and $-\log f_{\text{A}^-} = -4 \log f_{\pm}$)

where

d_M = optical density of pure HA or HA^-

d_i = optical density of pure A^- or A^-

d = optical density of a mixture of $\text{HA}(\text{HA}^-)$ or $\text{A}^-(\text{A}^-)$.

B-values were obtained from meter-readings, thus pK values were calculated. pK values were calculated with the help of Debye-Hückel equation and also from measurements at low ionic strengths. The results are given in Table I.

The ΔH 's of the ligands in 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane were obtained from the plot of pK against $1/T$. Other thermodynamic properties (ΔG and ΔS) have been determined in the usual way. These are given in Table 3.

The pK values of salicylic acid obtained by us at an ionic strength 0.1M at 25° are : 3.13 ± 0.02 (20%), 3.95 ± 0.04 (45%), 4.95 ± 0.05 (70%) and 6.31 ± 0.08 (82%).

The thermodynamic values using Debye-Hückel equation are : 3.40 ± 0.02 (20%), 4.44 ± 0.04 (45%), 6.25 ± 0.05 (70%) and 8.98 ± 0.08 (82%).

No systematic determination of pK 's of salicylic acid in mixed solvents have been reported in literature. The only work recorded is that of Van Uitert¹ who gave a value of 7.00 at 30° in mixed solvents containing 75% dioxane by weight.

To assess how far we are justified in using Debye-Hückel equation for the calculation of thermodynamic values in mixed solvents, we have also determined the pK 's at low ionic strengths ($\sim 10^{-4}M$). The results are : 3.45 ± 0.02 (20%), 4.37 ± 0.04 (45%), 6.10 ± 0.05 (70%) and 7.57 ± 0.08 (82%).

TABLE 1

System	% of dioxane by wt.	Temp. °C	Dissn. const. at $\mu = 0.1M$ K_e	Thermodynamic Dissn. const. using D-H eqn. K_a	Thermodynamic Dissn. Const. detd. at low ionic strengths ($\mu = 10^{-4}M$) K_a
Salicylic acid $HA \rightleftharpoons H^+ + A^-$	20%	25	7.41×10^{-4}	3.98×10^{-4}	3.57×10^{-4}
	30%	25			1.74×10^{-4}
	45%	25	1.12×10^{-4}	3.63×10^{-5}	4.26×10^{-5}
	70%	25	1.12×10^{-5}	5.62×10^{-7}	8.02×10^{-7}
		35	1.41×10^{-5}	6.46×10^{-7}	
		45	1.74×10^{-5}	7.59×10^{-7}	
	82%	25	4.90×10^{-7}	1.02×10^{-9}	2.67×10^{-8}
		35	6.92×10^{-7}	1.32×10^{-9}	
		45	9.55×10^{-7}	1.51×10^{-9}	
		0%		3.162×10^{-3}	
Sulphosalicylic acid $HA^- \rightleftharpoons H^+ + A^{2-}$	20%	25	1.29×10^{-3}		5.37×10^{-4}
	30%	25			2.32×10^{-4}
	45%	25	3.72×10^{-4}		5.01×10^{-5}
	70%	25	1.70×10^{-5}		6.31×10^{-7}
		35	2.04×10^{-5}		
		45	2.51×10^{-5}		
	82%	25	2.63×10^{-6}		6.61×10^{-8}
		35	3.72×10^{-6}		
	45	5.01×10^{-6}			

TABLE 2

Temp. = 25°

 ΔpK of acid in different dioxane water mixtures.

% age of dioxane	Formic acid	Acetic acid	Propionic acid	Salicylic acid	Sulphosalicylic acid
20	0.43	0.53	0.60	0.48	0.47
45	1.34	1.55	1.68	1.40	1.50
70	3.27	3.56	3.74	3.13	3.40
82	5.05	5.38	5.54	4.60	4.34

TABLE 3

Reaction	% of dioxane	ΔG in K cal/mole at 25°C	ΔH in K cal/mole	ΔS cal/deg.mole
$HA \rightleftharpoons H^+ + A^-$ (A^- = Salicylate anion)	20	+4.27		
	45	+5.39		
	70	+6.75	+4.11	-8.9
	82	+8.60	+6.28	-7.8
$HA^- \rightleftharpoons H^+ + A^{2-}$ (A^{2-} = Sulphosalicylate anion)	20	+3.93		
	45	+4.68		
	70	+6.50	+3.68	-9.4
	82	+7.61	+6.79	-4.7

We have already pointed out the pH -values obtained from meter readings as well as calculated from Harned and Owen's³ data are in good agreement in mixtures containing upto 70% dioxane. For 82% dioxane water mixture, the pK value based on meter-reading is 6.31, based on Harned's data is 5.42 whereas the value based on the redetermined value of Janz *et al.*³ is 5.76.

For sulpho-salicylic acid in different dioxane water media at an ionic strength of 0.1M at 25° we have for the pK 's, 2.89 ± 0.02 (20% by weight of dioxane), 3.43 ± 0.04 (45%), 4.77 ± 0.05 (70%) and 5.58 ± 0.08 (82%).

The evaluation of thermodynamic dissociation constant in case of sulphosalicylic acid presents a difficult problem. The dissociation constants of salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids at 0.1M (both in aqueous and in mixed solvents) show that sulphosalicylic acid (pK is lower) is stronger than salicylic acid (pK is higher). This is what one would expect as the introduction of sulphonic acid group enhances the acidic character of the carboxyl group. But the introduction of activity coefficients using Debye-Hückel equation makes salicylic acid stronger than sulphosalicylic acid particularly in mixed solvents. Sulphosalicylic acid is a comparatively big molecule and the two negatively charged groups $-SO_3^-$ and $-COO^-$ are considerably separated. As such it is likely that putting 2 for Z_i in the Debye-Hückel expression for the activity corrections is posing a problem. To clarify this we have determined the dissociation constants of sulphosalicylic acid at $\mu = 0.1M$ and at $\mu = 6 \times 10^{-4}M$ to $3 \times 10^{-3}M$ in aqueous solutions. The average pK values are 2.50 ± 0.02 at $\mu = 0.1M$ and 2.76 ± 0.02 (at $\mu = 6 \times 10^{-4}$ to $3 \times 10^{-3}M$) at 25°. The thermodynamic value is 2.80 using Debye-Hückel limiting law with $Z_i = 1$ and $2 \log f_-$ while with $Z_i = 2$ and $4 \log f_-$ we get 2.85 at 25°. The average pK may be put to 2.82 ± 0.02 . This shows that to get the thermodynamic values it is preferable to work in dilute solution. From the pK at $\mu = 0.1M$, the use of $Z_i = 2$ gives pK_T 2.98 and $Z_i = 1$, 2.74. A comparison of these with the value obtained from the data at low ionic strengths show that a value closer to $2 \log f_{\pm}$ rather than $4 \log f_{\pm}$ is involved by way of correction for variation of activity due to ionic strength indicating that the effective charge cannot be taken as two. So to get the thermodynamic dissociation constant we have worked in medium of low ionic strengths. The pK values of the dissociation constants determined at low ionic strengths ($\sim 10^{-4}M$) is 2.76 ± 0.02 in water, 3.27 ± 0.02 , 4.30 ± 0.04 , 6.20 ± 0.05 , 7.18 ± 0.08 in dioxane water media containing 20%, 45%, 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane.

The results at $\mu = 0.1M$ and at zero ionic strengths (except at 70% dioxane) suggest that sulphosalicylic acid is stronger than salicylic acid. The anomaly in case of 70% dioxane cannot be explained though the measurements of this percentage were repeated several times.

The pK 's of both salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids increase as the proportion of the organic component in the medium increases. It is found that the plot of pK vs. $1/D$ is linear at the low percentage of dioxane. Similarly, the linear relationship holds good if we plot pK vs. mole-fraction of the organic solvent. In table 2, ΔpK , i.e., $pK_s - pK_w$ (where the subscripts 'S' and 'w' mean the values in mixed-solvent and water respectively) at 25° for different acids³ (pK 's of formic, acetic and propionic acids and those from the present determination) are given ΔpK gives a measure of the change of free energy ($\Delta G_t = 2.303 RT\Delta pK$) on transferring the acid from water to the mixed solvent medium. Results indicate that the change in the free energy of transfer on adding the organic component is similar in all the cases.

The thermodynamic functions ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° for the acids are given in table 3. Analysis of the thermodynamic data is complex. Our results on the ligands show that the dissociation processes are endothermic. The endothermic character increases with the increase in organic solvent. This is reasonable as coulombic energies become greater and greater as the percentage of dioxane increases. The results also indicate that the dissociation involves creation of new fields which decrease entropy values. This is actually observed in practice in aqueous and in mixed solvents.

Ionization of neutral molecules to charged ions, according to Frank and Evans⁶ concept, accompany a decrease in entropy due to immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules around the ions. The entropy data on the dissociation of carboxyl group in salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids are lacking. The dissociation of ligands producing charged species invariably decreases the entropy (entropy value for the dissociation of carboxyl group is ~ 16 e.u.) but the process in these ligands results in the formation of anions which are stabilised by intramolecular hydrogen-bonding. Thus entropy change may be favourable compared to aliphatic acids. We see the same trends as in aliphatic acids except that the entropy values are more favourable.

In order to explore the role of the solvent, it is desirable to know the values of ion-solvent interaction. More data in the mixed solvents are needed before any definite postulate can be made.

The authors wish to thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for a research grant.

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Received July 26, 1968.